

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

“CATASTROPHE NOISE” AS (1) A NECESSARY CONDITION FOR THE SURVIVAL OF CIVILIZATION AND (2) AN UNREMOVABLE THREAT TO ITS EXISTENCE

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Abstract

The paper discusses the fundamental contradiction of evolution. On the one hand, evolution laws require sociums to develop, the termination of the development leads to sociums' death (“social production can exist only as expanded reproduction”). On the other hand, catastrophes (and stressful situations in general) are a driving force for development, because they stimulate evolutionary self-assemblies. That is why “catastrophe noise” is always present in the life of sociums. However, if its level is significantly higher or lower than some optimal level, the socium degrades and then perishes. To ensure their survival, sociums create special mechanisms – war, market, and science, which generate “catastrophe noise”. But sociums are not able to maintain “catastrophe noise” at an optimal level which, in principle, is incalculable. Because of the unremovable imperfection of the controlling of its “catastrophe noise”, civilization will sooner or later perish due to it, if it does not perish earlier from catastrophes of external origin.

Keywords: “catastrophe noise”, evolution, “effect of shaking” evolutionary systems, socium, civilization, war, market, science, professional defects of scientists.

Although Charles Darwin's theory has contributed most to the spread of evolutionary ideas generally accepted in science today, the specific mechanism he proposed for the emergence of evolutionary innovations – the mechanism of natural selection – should be recognized as untenable. The autogenetic concept, which assumes that evolution occurs as a result of the self-organization of matter, is becoming increasingly widespread today.

Note that the autogenetic concept has much deeper roots than the theory of natural selection. The origin of the idea on the self-moving force of interactions (matter) is lost in the haze of ages. The early evolutionists were spontaneous autogeneticists; they spoke of the self-development of matter carried out by means of natural forces. For example, René Descartes wrote about laws of nature that would be sufficient to make the parts of matter unravel and arrange themselves very orderly. Clearly, laws alone cannot move anything, everything is moved by forces, or interactions, the laws of which Descartes called the laws of nature, directly referring to gravitation. The evolutionary views of I. Newton, I. Kant, P. Laplace, E. Darwin, R. Chambers, and others were of a similar nature. The following section summarises in five points the main propositions of the author's version of this concept [1].

The outlines of an autogenetic evolutionary concept

1. **The autogenetic idea.** Following the autogenetic tradition, we believe that universal evolution, i.e. inorganic, organic, and social evolution considered in a unified way, is the result of the self-organisation of matter (interactions).

2. **Vector of evolution.** Evolution takes place in a certain direction; its vector has several components:

- increase of complexity;

- increase of diversity;
- intensification of interactions;
- intensification of cycles;
- increase in the connectedness of “everything to everything”;
- growth of systems openness (increasing role of interaction with the environment); etc.

These components are common to universal evolution on the whole. Material systems must evolve, i.e. change along the vector of evolution, otherwise they degenerate and perish: “He in whose life there is no change, perishes by it. “Dead” is that which cannot change on its own anymore” [2]. In the evolutionary competition, the systems that are more successful in directing their actions along the vector of evolution win each time and, accordingly, survive.

Terminology note. Sometimes we will be talking about the evolution of sociums and sometimes about the evolution of civilizations, keeping in mind that a civilization is also a socium, only big. In extreme case – the biggest one we know (human civilization on Earth).

3. **Evolution is the measure of all things.** The laws of evolution are part of a single set laws of nature that are obligatory for us. Sociums that go against the laws of evolution are doomed to perish. The meaning of human life lies in the best adherence to the laws of evolution. The maxim of Protagoras (5th century B.C.) “Man is the measure of all things” is untenable; in fact, the maxim “evolution is the measure of all things” works.

Evolution is not “concerned” with the interests of man or anyone else. The evolution of Neanderthal man which had transformed him about 40 thousand years ago in Cro-Magnon (the modern person), wiped out

Neanderthal man himself in about 5,000 years. The further course of events brought not much happiness to people. Although following the laws of evolution does not bring people happiness, evolution is unstoppable.

4. The evolutionary principle of minimax. Evolution does everything possible under given specific conditions, as if there were a law, which forces evolving systems not only to increase their complexity and variety of forms, not only to intensify metabolisms with cycles, etc., but also to do this as frugally as possible. By maximally intensifying the metabolisms, living organisms simultaneously minimize their losses by constantly solving the minimax tasks [3, 4]. Maximizing their income and making up more and more new pleasures of life, people minimize their expenditures on them. And so on.

The founder of the evolutionary morphology of animals A.N. Severtsov [5] has produced the idea that progressive improvements differ from non-progressive ones in that they open the way for further improvements. Let's start with this idea. Expenditure of energy is progressive when it sets the stage for later expenditure of energy. Money must make money. So – everywhere and in everything.

We arrive at the evolutionary principle of minimax: in each macroscopic fragment of the observable world, the intensity of interactions leading to their further intensification is maximized and the intensity of interactions not leading to their further intensification is minimized.

Both systems intensifying the interactions insufficiently and those doing it too quickly, overusing resources, lose the evolutionary competition. The USSR collapsed precisely because its economy and all social life were too costly, being carried out with catastrophic overuse of resources – human, material and energy.

5. The “effect of shaking” evolutionary systems. Imagine a plastic tray with a magnet on it and iron filings scattered randomly. When the tray is gently shaken, filings form a structure on the tray that reproduces magnetic lines of force.

When applied to evolution, this “shaking” is the “shaking” of evolutionary systems. The role of the magnetic field, which creates a constant pressure on the filings, which does not lead to visible consequences in “peaceful” time, is played here by the interactions that create a constant pressure on the evolving systems. The role of the “shaker” is played by catastrophes occurring on the Earth from time to time, which, starting with the book by Georges Cuvier [6], appear in the concepts of evolutionary catastrophism. For example, recall the plague pandemic of the 14th century in Europe:

“The plague pandemic of 1345–1349 so ravaged and devastated Europe that one would have expected a delay in the historical process. This, however, did not happen. Just in the fourteenth century, the development of bourgeois relations began in Italy (Florence), in Flanders, and partly in England” [7].

By creating stress pressures on evolving systems, catastrophic events of external origin dramatically increase the effect of internal interactions pressures on them, stimulating evolutionary self-assemblies. Under stress conditions, the evolving system becomes desta-

bilized and labile, the scope of arising mutations (innovations) expands until the system recover from the crisis.

However, evolutionary catastrophes can also occur for internal reasons. It has already become a cliché that social crises as a rule lead to great changes. Here, in its pure form, we have a manifestation of the “effect of shaking”: the crisis causes stressful pressure on socium members, stimulating evolutionary mental and behavioral self-assemblies, among which, due to the presence of a stochastic component in evolution, there are not only self-assemblies that contribute to the elimination of the roots of the crisis, but also self-assemblies “directed in different directions”. This is why such crises stimulate not only the transition to another socio-economic formation, but also the emergence of new trends in art, science, etc.

Our evolutionary “effect of shaking” echoes not only Cuvier's evolutionary catastrophism, but also Arnold Toynbee's concept of Challenge-and-Response. Whereas evolutionary catastrophism emphasizes catastrophes of external origin, according to Toynbee, external challenge is combined with internal stimulus. Moreover, Toynbee insists that the continuous development of civilization can only occur when it itself generates a successive chain of challenges:

“In so far as this grows and continues to grow, it has to reckon less and less with challenges delivered by external forces and demanded responses on an outer battlefield, and more and more with challenges that are presented by itself to itself in an inner arena. Growth means that the growing personality or civilization tends to become *its own* environment and *its own* challenger and *its own field of action*” [8].

“Catastrophe noise” as a necessary condition for the survival of civilization

So far, in describing the author's version of the autogenetic concept, we have followed the book [1]. Now we will go further and introduce the new concept – “catastrophe noise” (it is constructed by analogy with the term “white noise”).

What was said in the fifth point of the previous section means that catastrophes (and stressful situations in general) are a necessary component of the life of sociums, providing, in accordance with the evolutionary principle of the minimax, their evolution some optimal rate and, thus, their survival. In the absence of catastrophes, the evolutionary speed decreases, which leads the sociums to degradation and the consequent death. On the other hand, sociums are brought to death by catastrophes that are too destructive. We come to the conclusion that a certain optimal level of “catastrophe noise” in the life of a socium, determined by the evolutionary principle of minimax, should be present. If the actual level of “catastrophe noise” is higher or lower than the optimal level, the socium's evolution slows down; if it is significantly higher or lower, the socium perishes.

Let's talk about it once again. If all catastrophes are prevented, civilization will die because of an excessive reduction of the “catastrophe noise”, i.e. due to the disappearance of this driving force of evolution. If no action is taken to prevent catastrophes, civilization will

also perish, but from exceeding that level, i.e. from the destructive effects of catastrophes. The picture is enormously complicated the fact that the optimum level of “catastrophe noise” is in principle incalculable.

My contention (Arnold Toynbee did not say this, although it is in the spirit of his concept) is that civilization, in order to ensure its guaranteed survival, has created three specific mechanisms for generating catastrophes to speed up its evolution: war, market, and science. In other words, civilization creates “catastrophe noise”, as they say, with its own hands.

War as the generator of “catastrophe noise”

In the history of humanity, evolutionary breakthroughs were repeatedly brought about by devastating invasions of barbarians on this or that civilization. In some cases, their strike brought civilizations to ruin. In others, however, this collapse was not final; there was an “afterlife”: a new civilization arose on the ruins of the old one after the end of the recession, which could last for several “dark ages”; as a rule, this represented an evolutionary step forward.

So, classical Hellenic civilization emerged after and as a result of the destruction of the Cretan-Mycenaean civilization by the Achaeans (mid-15th century B.C.) and Dorians (around 1000 B.C.). The period between the twelfth and eighth centuries B.C. is the “dark ages” in the history of ancient Greece, after which it began to flourish. Its rise in the fifth century B.C. was, largely, due to the repulsion of Persian aggression.

Western civilization arose due to the invasion of the Western Roman Empire by the Huns, the Visigoths, and the Germans in V century A.D. Between the collapse of Western Roman Empire and the occurrence of Western civilization, three “dark ages” passed, through which Europe was transferred by Christianity. Already in the second half of the eighth century, Charlemagne created his empire, and from the end of the eleventh century, Western civilization, due to the excess of its power, shifted to expansion (crusades, conquest of the New World, etc.).

In many ways, it was war and military armaments that stimulated social evolution. For example, war directly participated in the emergence of cities through an almost continuous armed struggle between sociums. Medieval civilization in its European version could not have taken place without knightly arms, and would not have given way to an absolutist state without the creation of firearms. And so on and so forth.

The market as the generator of “catastrophe noise”

Wars stimulate social evolution very ineffectively, with enormous collateral damage. That is why, the social world has long ago created a much better mechanism to stimulate its evolution. It is the market, which, unlike war, provides a constant stress-pressure for members of socium, creating for them a “permanent disaster” effect and thus stimulating an evolutionary mental and behavioral self-assemblies.

Thus, being tuned to generating innovations, the market economy is constantly “shaken up”, continuously renewing itself and staying in the mode of “creative destruction” [9].

While working permanently and in a directed way,

market is more effective than war as a mechanism stimulating the evolution of socium. Moreover, the instability introduced by war prevents the market from functioning properly, reducing its efficiency. Therefore, throughout human history, sociums have tried, with varying success, to eschew war in favour of market. People are gradually learning to do without war, creating stressful pressure, necessary for evolution, on an individual through peaceful market means.

The twentieth century saw a turning point in the market's struggle against war, prompted by the transition in developed countries to Keynesian economics (the name derives from one of its fathers, John Keynes). In a nutshell, the Keynesian idea can be summarized as follows: high consumer demand and high wages do not only benefit employees, but also employers. Today, the Keynesian economy has been realised in the “Golden Billion” countries, where employees' wages are 40–70% of the value of production, which, by raising consumer demand, has brought the economy to fairly steady growth.

For the first time in human history, the Keynesian market made power conflicts between countries superfluous. It is not profitable for a country with Keynesian economy to exploit poor countries with low consumer demand, it is much more profitable to cooperate with rich partner countries with high consumer demand. It is therefore not in the interests of Keynesian countries to exploit poor countries, but rather to help them also become developed by making the transition to the Keynesian economy. The colonial system did collapse in parallel with the development of the Keynesian economy after World War II, because it became unprofitable. As a result, the market, as a more effective means of stimulating social evolution, began to win over the war. It is the fact that countries with Keynesian economies (post-industrialized countries) do not fight with each other.

Science as the generator of “catastrophe noise”

Neither war nor market aim directly at stimulating social evolution by generating innovations. This turns out to be a by-product of their actions, resulting in “catastrophe noise” (catastrophic and other stressful situations) that stimulates evolutionary self-assemblies. In the case of science, the situation is reversed: the generation of innovation is its immediate task, whereas “catastrophe noise” turns out to be a by-product of its activities.

Not just certain research fields such as nuclear physics, genetic engineering, and artificial intelligence, which are on everyone's lips, come out to be (or may come out to be) catastrophically dangerous. Scientific researches in many and very different areas, including some of the most seemingly innocuous, can turn out to be dangerous. What could be more innocuous than a socio-economic theory developed by an armchair scientist? Initially nobody could imagine that Karl Marx's theory would cause a global social upheaval (social catastrophe) with tens, if not hundreds of millions of victims.

But it is not only about the danger of these or other either scientific directions. All scientists, scientists as

such, are potentially dangerous, including the most brilliant and right-minded. Let us briefly discuss further the professional defects of scientists that make them generators of “catastrophe noise”.

1. Tendency to make untenable generalizations.

We are talking here about the principle of fallibilism, according to which any scientific theory, including the most fundamental and generally accepted, tomorrow may (or may not) be wrong. Thanks primarily to Karl Popper, who in the second half of the 20th century fundamentally substantiated this principle, it has been adopted by virtually the entire community of philosophers of science (but by no means by all scientists).

Today, there is nothing mysterious about the principle of fallibilism. Scientists' statements can be single (singular) and universal. The former are statements about single facts such as “the heat machine *A* has a cold reservoir”, “the heat machine *B* has a cold reservoir”, etc. The statement “all heat machines have cold reservoir” is universal. Scientific theories, that interpret empirical facts, are obtained by scientists by generalizing a finite number of single facts and giving their conclusions a universal meaning.

The problem is that any generalization is a roulette; by generalizing, a scientist can always get into trouble. A single violation of a universal statement is enough to disprove it. For example, we cannot 100% reliably prove the validity of the energy conservation law, because we are unable to enumerate by hand all possible cases of transformation of one form of energy into another. If even a single case of violation of this law is found, it will force us to stop regarding it as a universal law of nature.

Importantly, scientists are not only compelled by the nature of scientific knowledge to make non hundred percent justified generalizations, but are prone to them: they rush ahead of other scientists to be the first to declare their discovery (the struggle for priority is the driving force of scientific creativity).

2. Coding of readers and listeners by scientists.

The term “coding” is used here in approximately the same sense in which physicians talk about, for example, coding alcoholics with psychotherapeutic means.

In seeking to influence directly the subconscious of readers and listeners, the authors of scientific innovations often go beyond purely scientific arguments by applying the same persuasion technique as advertising, where the promoted product is shown to the public in conjunction with something that evokes obviously positive emotions. For example, they put funny kids and animals in advertising. As a result of repeated “reception” of ads we subconsciously develop a positive perception of the advertised product.

Following this recipe, the authors of scientific discoveries use key terms for their innovations, along with those that have a deliberately positive or negative connotation. “Average” scientists are also subject to the sin of coding: such are the general laws of thinking, not just scientific thinking. We all strive to express our thoughts as convincingly as possible, unconsciously using coding techniques. When coding each other, we most of all succumb to the coding by our great predecessors: brilliant scientists sometimes achieve astonishing results in

this genre.

Let us cite as an example the theory of natural selection that was discussed at the beginning of this paper. The specific mechanism proposed by Charles Darwin for the emergence of evolutionary innovations, i.e. the mechanism of natural selection, let's say mildly, is not indisputable. Nevertheless, Darwin's theory long supplanted competing evolutionary concepts. And, I believe, that was largely due to the “apt” name Darwin chose for his theory.

Indeed, the term “natural” carries no information about the specifics of Darwin's proposed mechanism of organic evolution. But it does suggest to the reader that it refers to something ordinary, normal, real, standard, usual, routine, reasonable, understandable (I have extracted from the dictionary some meanings of the word “natural”). Being absolutely incorrect for its scientific meaning, this choice turned out to be extremely effective in terms of coding: for a long time, as nothing else, it provided, at the subconscious level, a positive attitude of the scientific and near-scientific community to the theory of natural selection.

The second example is the antipode of the first. J.-B. Lamarck [10] thought the evolution of the organic world to be occurring as a result of the nature's self-development. According to Lamarck, the means by which nature creates more and more complex organic forms are interactions, among the various forms of which Lamarck gave priority to heat and electricity. No mysticism. Unfortunately, in accordance with the scientific language of the 18th century that nurtured him, Lamarck called the interactions that drive organic evolution *invisible fluids*, which were already considered as something mystical by scientists of the 19th century, and this shifted Lamarck's fully rational autogenetic conception of evolution from the proscenium of evolutionism for by almost two centuries.

3. Scientists adhere to outdated generalizations with all their might. The public conscience is set up to be too tolerant towards scientists. It is generally accepted that they are doing everything they can to get rid of their mistakes. Karl Popper's rendition of this myth is as follows:

“I do not know any creative scientist who wouldn't make mistakes – I mean the greatest of them: Galileo, Kepler, Newton, Einstein, Darwin, Mendel, Pasteur, Koch, Crick and even Hilbert and Gödel... Of course, we all understand that we should not be mistaken, and we are doing our best... At the same time, we are nevertheless sinful animals – sinful mortals, as the early Greek philosophers would say: only gods can know; we mortals can only express opinions and speculations” [11].

The pastoral, painted by Popper, has little to do with reality. Scientists try to get rid only of intra-paradigmatic errors: flaws in logic, errors in calculations, incorrect experiments. And most scientists do not hurry to get rid of paradigmatic errors that arise from unfortunate generalization of a group of single facts. On the contrary, they defend canonical theories to the last bullet, despite those theories fail under the pressure of new empirical facts.

There are three main factors to blame for the occurrence of this professional defect of scientists. **Firstly**, the coding of potential opponents by the authors of scientific innovations, discussed above.

Secondly, the phenomenon of imprinting, discovered by Konrad Lorenz in the animal world and also acting in the world of people, including science. If newly hatched ducklings or chicks are presented with a moving balloon or a cardboard box, then they will follow it everywhere as their mother, not being able to “critically reconsider” their attitude towards it. Something similar happens to young scientists: we all tend to regard the scientific ideas we are taught as immutable truths, the revision of which becomes extremely difficult for us.

Thirdly, the scientific community's continued rejection of the principle of fallibilism, discussed in point 1 of this section. Most scientists still adhere to the concept of the cumulative growth of scientific knowledge, according to which new truths are added at each current moment in time to the old ones, while all previously obtained truths are retained. Cumulativism has collapsed under the influence of facts which say that the development of science is different: in science it is the norm to discover the fallacy of old theories and to develop new ones in their place.

It is clear that if you believe that scientific knowledge is a set of 100% reliably established truths and that its development is a process of accumulation of such truths, a triumphant march from one truth to another, then for you the ideas of our great predecessors are unquestionable truths. This is the position of the modern community of scientists, with rare exceptions.

The combination of these three factors works flawlessly. It becomes clear why the modern scientific community sees the great scientists of the past as prophets of absolute truth.

Of course, there is nothing wrong with honouring the great scientists of the past in itself. It is not good if and when this reverence is excessive. And so it becomes when we identify weaknesses in a given scientific theory, which we inherited, and we defend it at all costs with sincere faith in its truth, distorting facts and logic. A talented (and all the more so, a brilliant) scientist has no problem finding new theoretical justification for an inherited universal statement (generalization) that he or she considers valid, and the old theoretical justification of which ended in a fiasco.

4. The scientific community is dominated by an atmosphere of rejection of scientific dissent. This is happening for the same reason: because most scientists continue to believe in the immutability of the scientific truths they produce. Any scientific dissidence, any deviation from the mainstream, any deviation from a particular school of thought or even from the point of view of a particular scientist, is perceived by that particular scientist, by that particular school of thought or the mainstream scientific community (the scientific establishment) negatively. The harshest resistance is caused by the most innovative works.

5. The penchant of scientists for sociopathy. Driven by the desire to make scientific discoveries and perpetuate themselves in the annals of science, some

(many?) scientists – otherwise perfectly normal people – become sociopaths devoid of empathy, capable of pushing through their discoveries at any cost, disregarding their danger to people.

As proof, I will briefly retell David Reimer's heart-breaking story, which took place in Canada and the USA and is described in Francis Fukuyama's book [12], which in turn follows John Colapinto's book “As Nature Made Him: The Boy Who Was Raised as a Girl”. Reimer was born a boy in 1965. As an infant, he had problems urinating due to phimosis. He was circumcised at the age of 8 months for this reason, but it was not done very well.

This is where the famous psychologist and sexologist John Money comes in. To test his hypothesis (Money believed that a person's gender identity is not determined by nature, but is instilled by the environment) he persuaded the boy's parents to change his sex, including complete castration. Reimer had not only the remnants of his penis, but also sex glands removed, and he had the rudimentary female external genitals formed. He was then supposed to be raised as a girl and an operation to create a vagina was planned for his adolescence. It ended tragically: as a teenager, Reimer resolutely refused the planned operation, then attempted to create a two-parent family with his wife and adopted children, but at the age of 38 he committed suicide, which his parents blamed on Money's methodology.

To be clear. Money has shown himself to be a sociopath, but not a psychopath. The difference is that a psychopath's lack of empathy is the result of genetic predisposition, whereas a sociopath's one is influenced by his environment. Money's sociopathic stamp was imposed on him by his profession. As Fukuyama writes, “John Money was driven by a combination of scientific vanity, ambition, and the desire to make an ideological point, characteristics that led him to overlook contrary evidence and work directly against the interests of the patients” [13].

It is this obsession of scientists with developing and promoting their own scientific innovations that makes otherwise wholesome and mentally healthy scientists potentially dangerous to the people. Many of scientists do so under the assumption that they are working “for the good of mankind”. This attitude, I believe, is extremely dangerous, allowing a scientist, when “necessary”, to justify any violations of generally accepted moral standards.

When a scientist decides that he has made, or is about to make, a major discovery, he “goes mad” as far as his potential discovery is concerned, turning into a “sociopath of directional action” with no empathy for people. The main thing for him in this state is to make a world discovery “for the good of mankind”, and thus to become famous. And everything else can go to hell. He is ready to risk both his own fate and the fate of others, both of individuals and of the entire humanity for its, humanity's, benefit.

Characteristically, John Money did not suffer any punishment under the law. Nor was he ostracized by his colleagues. There was only criticism of his hypothesis by those who did not share it. In this case this reaction

of the scientific community, in my opinion, characterizes it (the scientific community) in a quite sociopathic way.

Let us emphasize once again that, for the vast majority of scientists, the penchant for sociopathy is manifested only when it comes to developing and promoting their discoveries, and in everyday life, scientists are perfectly normal people, not sociopaths. Thus, a scientist is prone to sociopathy precisely as a scientist, i.e. as a person working in science. Thus, he is a dangerous for civilization in exactly that capacity.

As far as I know, the predisposition of scientists to become sociopathic has not yet been discussed in the scientific literature. Instead, the ethical neutrality of science has been discussed. These two phenomena are related, because an ethically neutral person is simply a beautiful label for a person deprived of compassion, or empathy, for people, i.e. a sociopath. You can talk about a person's lack of empathy, or you can talk about their ethical neutrality, which is essentially the same thing.

To sum up our invectives against scientists, we must admit that the scientific community sorely lacks a critical attitude to itself and empathy for people. That is on the one hand. On the other hand, science has placed such powerful forces of nature at the service of humanity that the actions of even a single scientist or a single scientific laboratory (say virological one) can lead to a global catastrophe. This combination is extremely dangerous for civilization.

“Catastrophe noise” as an unremovable threat to the existence of civilization

Let's briefly recap the plot of the paper again. Catastrophes (and stressful situations in general) have an ambivalent effect on sociums, manifesting the fundamental contradiction of evolution. On the one hand, by destroying established structures, catastrophes contribute to the stagnation and demise of sociums. On the other hand, the same catastrophes stimulate evolutionary self-assemblies, which helps sociums evolve and thus survive. That is why, there is always “catastrophe noise” in the life of sociums. If, however, it is above or below some optimal level, the socium degrades; if it is significantly above or below, the socium perishes.

To ensure its survival as long as possible, a civilization generates “catastrophe noise” for itself by creating special mechanisms: war, market, and science. War was the first to enter the game, and for a long time it dominated. Wars made geopolitical sense, when it made sense to seize territories. And it made sense when agriculture dominated the economy, and the more territories a country had, the more successful it was. In the second half of the twentieth century, with the establishment of the Keynesian economy in the “Golden Billion” countries, the situation changed. While in the nineteenth century, the agriculture of the now developed countries employed the bulk of the economically active population, today it employs only 2%–6%. With the decline in the importance of agriculture for economy, the conquest of territory and wars with it, lost their meaning. Accordingly, the market has come forward as the generator of “catastrophe noise” in the life of sociums, and today there is already science, which

seems to have a great future in this respect.

With regard to the “catastrophe noise” generated by war, market, and science, the fundamental contradiction of evolution remains valid. If the catastrophes they generate are excessively devastating, it leads civilization to ruin. If, on the contrary, the catastrophes they generate do not reach the optimal level of “catastrophe noise”, the speed of social evolution declines, which again leads to the degradation and destruction of civilization.

It is extremely significant that the optimal level of “catastrophic noise” in principle cannot be calculated. There is no way to quantify the total impact of the catastrophes on socium: whether and to what degree they contribute to societal development or, on the contrary, to societal degradation. These quantifications are impossible neither in the gross: for all the catastrophes in the life of a given socium over a certain period of time, nor in details: for each individual catastrophe taken individually. Economists have already learned to measure the material damage from catastrophes in money, but the relationship of this material damage to the evolutionary future of socium remains unknown, because it is absolutely unclear how to estimate the evolutionary outcome of catastrophe-induced evolutionary self-assemblies.

Although it is impossible to calculate the level of “catastrophe noise” in principle, civilization, as it has no other way out, tries to manage it by finding its optimal level by experience. Naturally, this does not work out very well in all three cases: war, market, and science.

1. **War.** Being unaware of the evolutionary significance of war and the evolutionary ambivalence of its nature, people, nevertheless, have long tried to bring wars into some kind of framework, to regulate and limit them, to grope an unknown optimum level for the “catastrophic noise” that they generate. There were introduced “rules of war”, rules for treating prisoners of war and civilian population, bans on the use of chemical and nuclear weapons; also, international laws of war were introduced and developed. But all measures taken by civilization to put war on the right track are unremovably palliative and they do not give one hundred percent guarantee. Even today, war can spiral out of control and cause a global nuclear catastrophe, with the destruction of civilization as the final outcome. This is confirmed by the events caused by the special operation of the Russian Armed Forces in Ukraine that began on 24 February 2022 (as it is called by the Russian authorities; in the world it is called, to put it mildly, otherwise).

2. **Market.** What was the original task of civilization when it created the market? It was to ensure that the market creates stressful pressures on its participants, but that these pressures are neither too weak nor too strong. Too much pressure is put on market participants by criminals and the state. That is why sociums impose laws to protect the market from them. Independent branches of government, free elections, etc., – in short, all these democratic institutions limit government interference in the market. In turn, law enforcement structures, administrative and criminal laws limit the intervention of criminals in the market. But, as in

the case of war, all the measures that civilization has taken to bring market into some kind of framework are unremovably palliative, providing no ironclad guarantee. The market is now and again breaking out of the control of socium, and then economic, financial and political crises occur, which sometimes take on a global character and which may one day end badly for civilization.

3. **Science.** If civilization has tried to bring war and market into some framework, to grope an unknown optimum level for the “catastrophic noise” that they generate, then so far very little has been done to bring science into the framework. The real work is carried out, perhaps, only in one scientific field – in medical and biological research on humans in order to protect them from overzealous scientists. De facto science today is a virtually unregulated source of “catastrophe noise”. Considering the ever-increasing power of science, where the awkward actions of even one scientist can lead to a global catastrophe, this situation is extremely dangerous for civilization.

It seems to me that, in order to survive, civilization will have to develop legislation for science similar to that made for war and market, but taking into account the specific nature of science. It is necessary to provide administrative and criminal prosecution of scientists for violations of the legal regulations that will be devised in this area.

The direction of measures to control science is clear. This, of course, is tracking dangerous scientific research and restricting it. But not only: by compensating, as far as possible, for the professional defects of scientists, science could increase its effectiveness in accomplishing its primary task of producing evolutionary innovations, which will reduce the need for dangerous research. In the light of what I have said about science in the previous section, I believe the following measures are necessary:

- A change in the whole atmosphere of scientific life towards the development of an attitude favourable to scientific dissidence;
- Fighting the cult of great scientists as bearers of absolute scientific truth;
- Changing the whole philosophy of rewarding scientists: prizes should be awarded for new large-scale, intelligently presented ideas, without requiring them to be true, given that controversial and even erroneous ideas can be extremely fruitful;
- Condemning and possibly penalizing scientists for “coding” colleagues, i.e. using unscientific persuasion techniques based on advertising techniques;
- Restricting or even banning anonymous reviewing;
- The involvement of “juries” selected by lot from “ordinary” citizens, in the control of science so that they can prevent the sociopathic excesses of scientists.

Unfortunately, in general, the situation with the of protection civilization from science is similar to that with war and market: all measures to prevent dangerous scientific researches, including those mentioned here, are unremovably palliative. We know that scientific researches must be controlled to ensure some optimal

level of their catastrophicity. But we do not know what the optimal level of catastrophicity for all scientific researches is. This optimal level is in principle incalculable and can only be groped by experience.

Conclusion

The above can be extended to all catastrophe generating mechanisms created by civilization: not only to war, market, and science, but also to others, perhaps left out of the author's field of vision. The problem of incalculable optimal level of “catastrophe noise” has no constructive solution in principle. There is no cognitive tool, no practical considerations that allow us to understand that this particular catastrophe brings us closer to the optimal level of “catastrophe noise”, and another, on the contrary, distances us from it.

As far as I know, the only practical consideration of this kind, and by the way, it is widely applied today in the world – is the so-called *precautionary principle* adopted in 1992 at the UN Conference on Environment and Development. According to it, if there are threats of serious or irreversible damage to the environment, the lack of scientific basis for threat assessments should not be used as a reason to postpone the implementation of measures aimed at preventing it.

It seems obvious that widespread adherence to the precautionary principle will lead to an uncontrolled reduction of the level of “catastrophe noise” in the life of a civilization, which will cause an evolution inhibition dangerous for its existence.

We come to the conclusion, and this is the main conclusion of our paper, that civilization is doomed by the laws of evolution to dig its own grave. To survive, it generates in operation mode “catastrophe noise”, which level cannot be controlled adequately in principle. Civilization can only grope the optimal level of “catastrophe noise” by experience, getting bumps and bruises. Because of the unremovable imperfection of the controlling of the “catastrophe noise” it generates, civilization will sooner or later perish from it, if it would not perish earlier from catastrophes of external origin.

To console the reader, it can be said that this is, as described here, how the entire everyday life of human individuals does on in the sense that it all runs in a fog of uncertainty and unpredictability of the results of our actions and our future. We achieve everything by experience, by getting bumps and bruises. What lies ahead, and this is the only thing which is assured, is death from old age or as a result of our own mistake. Unless, of course, we perish in a catastrophe external to the individual. The life of human civilization in many ways, if not in the main one, is similar to that of a human individual.

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